

THE IMPORTANCE OF PUBLIC EVENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8032178>

Annotation: The article mainly discusses the importance of public events in the field of tourism and the prospects for its further development. The article also discusses the development of public events to mitigate tourist seasonality in our country. Taking into account the increase in tourist flow in our republic in recent years, it is important the further development of public events. Because it plays a big role in alleviating seasonality, which has been a problem for several years. By developing public events, we will have the opportunity to develop local and international tourism. Because many guests are interested in local customs, parties and animation programs in that region.

Keywords: tourism, public events, customs, resources, seasonality, domestic tourism, international tourism.

INTRODUCTION

The consumer market for tourist services is currently booming, including not only excursions but also entertainment programs. Several of the world's tourism components have proven to be the most successful venues for outstanding events. It is essential for animated outstanding theatrical programs to grab the attention and stimulate viewers for the purpose for introducing them to cultural customs, the long history of the nation as a whole, and comprehending its distinctive characteristics, which is why numerous tourists visit various places throughout the world.

Traditional methods of collective action are becoming increasingly obsolete. The manners of celebration are varied, as are the wide range of the category of collective festivities, which present themselves in a distinct and distinctive manner between the populations of every continent. Participants are bound together by a need to convey their feelings about political and social developments in an overwhelming performance and develop a celebratory performance based on national folklore.

Any public spectacle or holiday is the outcome of the coordination of recreational and cultural events. It all revolves around how well the outside factors of theatrical programs match the needs and wants of tourists [8].

An examination of the evolution of global tourism reveals that its efficacy depends extensively on the growth of a very prosperous and distinguished sector of entertainment. In recent years, ensuring the successful conducting of massive events, i.e. those incorporating an enormous amount of people, has become more and more important for the development of this field. Many foreign and domestic visitors attend well-organized public events. These kinds of occasions generate ongoing requirements for every kind of tourism-related service, including marketing, the reservation process, tourist transport, lodging, dining, culture, recreational activities, knowledge, insurance coverage, sports, health, and excursion support,

and so on [1]. There is currently no widely acknowledged categorization of mass tourism activities.

The act of planning and advertising an event in a city, area, or continent with the intention of attracting local and/or foreign travelers is known as events tourism. An event might include a variety of activities such as music festivals, sporting events, religious dates arts, charity events, food and drink, and much more. Event tourism is under the tourism umbrella, and it is not only a significant contribution to the world economy, but it is also a field of study in conjunction with the management of events.

Events may serve to spur domestic expansion. An effective celebration can increase the area's profile through media coverage, which will in turn draw more tourists, create jobs nearby, and support the argument for local infrastructure upgrades. Numerous tourism organizations have vowed to support event promotion because of the positive effects that they provide for a nation's economy [9].

LITERATURE REVIEW

There have been more studies on the subject, although most of them focus on organizations and companies rather than specific locations and vacation spots. While the emotional, geographical, interpersonal, and financial consequences constitute the primary objective of these studies, how they are applied to destinations suggests another aspect. Since these are a combination of products and services, it is important to take into account the unique qualities of each place.

The authors of the paper explore the impact events have on the development of government initiatives in destinations from their understanding of the visitor experience. The study theoretically investigates the relationships between the significance of integrating tourist wishes with destination experiences (tourism experience) and the capacity to coordinate and sustain the realization of the tourist potential [3].

There isn't a single, broadly recognized term that describes an event. The description of events and the numerous terminologies used for defining them have been covered extensively by authors. Nevertheless, there is little consensus over the appropriate names, explanations, or classifications. Because numerous writers define specific events in various manners, the disparities become apparent. The majority of authors concur that events are services in the economic sense, and differing definitions of events are a result of the unique qualities of the environments in which particular authors labor and produce their works. Additionally, because of how adaptable the events are, their definition can be altered to fit a variety of circumstances [5].

Events play a significant role in the development and marketing strategies of the majority of destinations as they are a key driver of tourism. Well-documented functions and effects of scheduled events in the tourism industry are becoming more crucial for the competitiveness of destinations. However, 'event tourism' was only recently developed in the tourism and travel sector as well as in the academic community, thus the subsequent growth of this industry can only be characterized as remarkable.

Additionally, the tourism sector has emerged as a key player in the achievement and allure of scheduled events, and "event management" is a rapidly expanding specialty in which travelers represent a potential customer base. However, not every event must be tourism-focused, and some people worry about the possible drawbacks of embracing a marketing-focused approach [7].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The popularity of mass action is deviating more and more from typical forms. The category of mass celebrations has many different shapes and kinds, and each of these manifestations is unique and peculiar to the peoples of the world. They are brought together by a shared ambition to create a celebratory spectacle that centers on local folklore and to openly share their opinions on social and political events.

The number of animation programmes that allow for the expansion of amazing tourism's bounds is rather well saturating the foreign tourist market.

Any large-scale event or festival is the outcome of the planning of both cultural and recreational pursuits. It all relies on how well the outside conditions of theatrical productions align with the requirements and preferences of tourists.

A fundamental feature of social life, dramatic vacations represent the lives of all individuals and the community as an entire entity. Although some holiday theatre productions are based on actual events and facts, they have significant teaching potential. Dramatic performances utilized during celebrations set a particular psychological tone, convey an encouraging emotional impose, uplift the spirits, and are a part of the holiday's theology. These days, when those around them no longer celebrate, when they are under continual stress when they rarely allow themselves to enjoy holidays and breaks, this is felt much more keenly. Additionally, animated events are designed to assist people regain a normal psychological state by giving them a vacation from their troubles and allowing them to experience the joy of life and their surroundings.

There are a number of requirements for public events.

Significant festival initiatives have an effect on boosting the legitimacy of the entire country as a forward-thinking nation that upholds its national customs and cultural heritage. The event may help encourage and strengthen ethnic pride while promoting the growth of different peoples' cultures. The opportunity for art enthusiasts to realize their own potential is one of the festival's most significant goals, it should be underlined. Every year, tens of thousands of amateur performers of various ages participate in them.

The mental and educational advantages of such festivals cannot be overstated because the sole motivators for these individuals are their love of the arts and a talent endowed by nature.

Originality, outstanding performance, and the ambition to transcend ordinary tasks constrained by theatre boundaries may be among the festival's major ideas. The festivals can thus accommodate the population's widest range of interests both geographically and conceptually. Additionally, the news coverage improves the festival management's standing in regard to elected officials, supporters, and other interested organizations. The reason for this enthusiasm is that events and traditional celebrations contribute significantly to the financial and social well-being of the nation, have an impact on the socio-cultural environment in the locations where they are held, and draw attention via the use of marketing and communication tools [8].

In terms of tourism, animation can be described as:

- animation gatherings (carnival processions, masquerades, film festivals, competition programmes, etc.)
- animated theatre productions (such as jousting contests, humorous clown shows, gladiator battles, costume balls, and character meet-up events).
- animated exhibits (museum performances, costume displays).

CONCLUSION

The major goal is to make the visitor feel at ease, keep him engaged, make him feel like a part of the programme, and help him remember his holiday as his favourite leisure. Recently, an increasing number of tourism businesses have started to handle the provision of animation services. Animators are experts at planning leisure time in resorts, sanatoriums, and other medical facilities, as is common knowledge. When someone says the word "animator," they frequently follow it up with the phrase "great entertainer." However, the definition of animation in recent times is a little broader. In the tourism industry, animation is seen as the process of creating and offering unique programmes for leisure time.

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